

PEDAGOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF EDUCATING STUDENTS IN THE SPIRIT OF NATIONAL VALUES

Khakimova Marhabo

teacher of Preschool education faculty of Uzbekistan-Finland
Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7860942>

Abstract: This article talks about developing the young generation with the help of national values, in the national spirit, and raising them to be loyal to the Motherland, morally and politely.

Keywords: education, training, ethics, manners, human, knowledge, national values, spirituality, student, youth, human.

Youth is the most responsible period of a person's life, because it is during this period that every person goes through the process of getting on his feet, forming, physically and socially coming of age. During this period, the spiritual world and moral image of young people, personal taste, mood, interest, and feeling of love change several times. If the society and family follow the life of young people correctly, it is a period of self-awareness, feeling the various complexities of life, especially gaining knowledge and life experience. In the development of independent Uzbekistan, the formation of national loyalty, first of all, the strengthening of independence, the formation and upbringing of a healthy generation in the national spirit are of great importance. The unique characteristics of our nation and its high moral duties form the core of national values. We have made it our mission to educate the young generation with the help of national values and in the national spirit. The process of education and upbringing of young people starts from primary school. From when, in what way and in what manner should we teach our children our national values, customs and traditions."

These opinions are a clear expression of the state order placed on the education system. The reflection of national and spiritual rules in the education of young people is the age-old dream of our people. Raising the morale of society is a priority direction of state policy. We need to raise free, well-rounded people who rely on their own strength and capabilities, who approach the events and events happening around them with an independent attitude, who see their personal interests in harmony with the interests of the country and the people. We should all understand that the effectiveness of our reforms in other areas of our lives, first of all, the revival of the people's spirituality, the extensive study of our rich historical heritage, the preservation of our traditions, the development of culture and art, science and education. we are witnessing that it is inextricably linked with. From the first years of independence, the government of our republic paid attention to creating a physically healthy and intellectually mature person. New subjects such as "fundamentals of spirituality", "idea of national independence", "patriotism" were introduced in schools, higher and secondary special educational institutions, and our history was illuminated anew. The memory of our ancestors who fought for our independence and were executed has been restored. A national idea and a national ideology began to form in the minds of young people and students.

People with high spirituality make the country known and famous. Spirituality begins with education. It is a well-known fact that there is no spirituality without education. The rank and color of things and events that make a nation a nation is due to education. As we mentioned above, the formation of national consciousness and national thinking, raising spirituality and enlightenment to a higher level is the demand of today. These important problems can only be solved through education. Indeed, the wisdom of education is the power of independence. By the power of independence, it is necessary to understand the high level of human intellect, the prosperity of the society and the state in which these people live, and the reputation of the world. This greatness is achieved only through education. That is why our ancestors attached great importance to education in the first place. By education, it is necessary to explain the various relations, activities, actions, interactions between the teacher and the student. Human spirituality and enlightenment are the product of education, intellectual intelligence, high morals and manners, brilliant talent and wisdom, religion and courage, and the like. As the teacher Safo Ochil said, "A person can be educated in two ways: through the direct influence of others, that is, teaching, as well as by reading the thoughts, teachings and works of the wise; a person can draw appropriate conclusions from his thinking, people's behavior, what he has done and is doing; "The most powerful thing is that it can be brought up through the means of thinking," they said. So, the word "educator" means not only parents, kindergarten teachers or school teachers-educators, but also all our social ancestors of the land, neighbors, village, neighborhood, and their works. Being proud of past scholars, generation - ancestors, perfect study of their heritage begins with national education. Therefore, the wisdom of education should be considered as the power of perspective. Indeed, education is an incomparable power for national independence and its bright future. Belief in the human mind and consciousness, soul, human duty, justice, humanitarianism, kindness, friendship, loyalty, Uzbek modesty, and chastity are inculcated through education.

The main goal of education is to develop and implement effective organizational and pedagogical forms and tools based on the rich national, spiritual and historical traditions of the people, customs and universal values in the spiritual and moral education of the young generation. Education of nationalism and patriotism in students with unity of words and work is an important aspect of the process of formation and independence of our country. It is impossible to educate a true person who perceives his people as a state in his community and a lover of his homeland without educating his people to love and respect their traditions, language and culture. A person with high national pride can fight for the future of the country and the happiness of the people. National pride is directly related to national identity. Awareness of national identity plays a very important role in human destiny. Values play an incomparably greater role in understanding national identity. The components of the concept of national identity were initially determined to include the following: Realization of belonging to the nation (ethnos), understanding the national unity and the existence of other ethnic groups.

Knowing the historical place of this nation in human development.

Loyalty to national values.

To understand the needs and interests of the nation, to know the ways of its development.

Pursuit of national independence and national development.

Patriotism and others.

As we have mentioned above, with the emergence of humanity, its language, customs, traditions, religion, culture, morals and decency norms expressing goodness began to emerge. Their content reflects the people's way of life, mentality, spirituality, standards of public morality, dreams and thoughts about the future prosperous life. The spiritual and cultural wealth that has passed the tests of time is being enriched in content, polished and rising to the level of value. That is why every people, nation has its own history and values related to it. These national values serve as an important tool in the realization of national identity. Each nation has its own language, spirituality and enlightenment, nature, morals, religion, faith, history, literature and art, cultural monuments, unique values, customs, traditions, social development, etc. constitute the identity of the nation. Understanding the national core is the history, material wealth, religion, culture, literature, art, moral and spiritual behavior, behavior and action criteria of each nation and people, customs and traditions. It means the power of desire to know the meaning and essence of one's parents, to be proud of them, to enrich them in terms of form and content, to pass them on to future generations, and to show them to other nations.

The ancient Greek philosopher Socrates (469-399 BCE) said: "A self-aware person understands what is useful for him and what he is capable of. He satisfies his desire and achieves happiness while doing what he can. It will be free from any mistakes and misfortunes. As a result, he can appreciate other people and use them for good. As a result, he will save himself from trouble." These wise words of Socrates encourage self-awareness. With the emergence of humanity, its language, customs, traditions, religion, culture, morals and decency norms expressing goodness began to emerge. In their content, the people's way of life, mentality, spirituality, standards of behavior and manners, dreams and thoughts about a future prosperous life are reflected, spiritual and material wealth that has passed the tests of time is enriched in content, polished to the level of value. is growing.

That is why every people, nation has its own history and values related to it. Values are important in the life and development of society, they are the product of social-historical development and an important factor of the spiritual maturity of society. From time immemorial, our ancestors have tried to reveal the social-political, cultural, educational and educational importance of values and their role in the life and development of society by approaching them from anthological, epistemological, heuristic and worldview points of view.

References:

1. Ashurov M.O. The education system of the Uzbek people - Samarkand Ziyokor, 2003, issue 6, pp. 16-24.
2. Yoldosheva Saodat Folk customs - customs and traditions. - Tashkent creative world publishing house. 2003 3-22 p.
3. Musurmonova O. Life and life program. - T.: Teacher, 1993
4. Achil Safo Spirituality of independence and foundations of education - T.; Teacher, 1997. Page 3.
5. Tulenov J. Philosophy of values - T.; Uzbekistan in 2010. 5 – 108b.
6. Anthology of Uzbek pedagogy. Compiler - authors K. Hoshimov, S. Ochil - T.; Teacher, 1995. 164b.
7. Kuronov M. School spirituality and national education - T.; Science. 2016 118b.

